

ON THE VIBRATION OF GLASS/POLYESTER COMPOSITE STIFFENED AND UNSTIFFENED RECTANGULAR PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Vibration studies have been undertaken on glass reinforced polyester composite stiffened and unstiffened plates to optimise the dynamic properties. Boundary conditions, stiffeners and orthotropy of the material add to the complexity of a mathematical solution and to overcome this problem it is possible to undertake experimental and analytical studies. These techniques have been used to investigate the modal behaviour of stiffened and unstiffened plates made from randomly orientated and bidirectional glass/polyester laminates with boundary conditions which are completely free, free/clamped and fully clamped.

The randomly orientated fibre and bidirectional composites have fibre volume fractions of 20% and 38% respectively. In the investigations the total mass of stiffeners is kept constant and each stiffened plate has either one or three stiffeners; the stiffeners have the same depth throughout.

The paper presents and compares plate modal analyses which are undertaken by experimental and analytical techniques. The former method is carried out by impact hammer and spectrum analysis and the latter method is undertaken using a standard finite element compute package for vibration analyses.

It is shown that an effective method of removing the natural frequencies of the system from the region where excitation energy is being produced is to optimise the dynamic properties.

INTRODUCTION

Structures manufactured from randomly orientated and bidirectional reinforcement are used in many fields of engineering including architectural engineering through to the high technologies of the aerospace industries. Plates do not act in isolation but are generally a part of a more complex assembly where the boundary conditions must be specified at the plate edge; in this condition the plate can be investigated separately.

Plates which are under dynamic loading can develop large amplitudes of vibration at resonance and could suffer a significant over-strain as a result. This could cause failure of the plate from fatigue during service life. One method of overcoming this problem is to displace the natural frequency of the plate from the range of those frequencies causing the resonance. This may be achieved by introducing stiffeners to the plate placed parallel to the shortest edge of the plate or by modifying the boundary conditions.

The object of this paper is to investigate the dynamic effects of stiffeners on an isotropic and an orthotropic fibre matrix composite laminated plate. The total distributed mass of stiffeners is kept constant but the number will be varied between zero and three per plate. The positions of these plates have been shown in fig 1. The

height and the sum of the widths of the rectangular stiffeners will also be kept constant. In addition to the rectangular beam stiffeners top hat stiffeners are being investigated analytically, but further studies are required before their results can be discussed.

Two techniques have been used during the investigation; the experimental one utilises accelerometers, a wave form analyser and a transfer function software package and the analytical one uses a standard computer package to obtain a solution for the eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

THE THEORETICAL TECHNIQUE

An exact mathematical solution of the displacement w of a plate can only be readily obtained for two boundary conditions; these are for the case of four edges simply supported and for the case of two opposite edges which have the same fixity. For any other boundary condition a solution tends to be very complex.

In many cases the boundary conditions, stiffeners and orthotropy of the material can create mathematical difficulties and it may not be possible to represent the shape function accurately, consequently numerical techniques are applied.

A finite element analysis, employing the ABAQUS program* has been used in the current investigation. In this program the subspace iteration method, which is presented in references [1], [2], is the basic algorithm used in the program; the procedure is a simultaneous inverse power iteration in which a small set of base vectors is created. A 'subspace' is defined and is transformed by iteration into the space containing the lowest few eigenvectors of the overall system at which point these lowest eigenpairs and hence natural frequencies of vibration are naturally available.

A preliminary investigation to determine the most suitable elements in the ABAQUS library was undertaken and fig 2a shows the final layout of the elements into which the plate was divided; the 100 element array was used for all unstiffened models, those plates which contained three stiffeners were divided into 150 elements.

Eigenvalue extractions were performed and the fundamental and harmonic frequencies were determined.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

Both a hammer and a shaker were used to excite the plates through their resonant frequencies and piezoelectric accelerometers monitored the response of the plates; the former through a frequency wave recorder to a Hewlett-Packard mini computer in which an Acquire software package enabled the computations of the frequency response function (F.R.F.) to be made, the latter was monitored through an oscillator and double beam oscilloscope to an x-y plotter.

The plate was first impulsed with a hammer (at, say, position r fig 1) which had a force transducer mounted on its head. A piezoelectric accelerometer was attached to the point where the response was measured (at, say, position s). The excitation signal and the response signal were stored in a DL 1200 wave form recorder via the charge amplifier. In the current investigation a Fast Fourier Transform (F.F.T.) was used to convert a time function to its frequency components.

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The time function is sampled every ΔT of a total time window of (N. ΔT). The data can be sampled between $2\mu s - 20$ ms for a total of 4095 samples per channel; the final choice of time depends upon the frequency range of interest. Generally, however, only 1024 points of the data are used so that reflections and multiple impacts are removed from the signals. In addition, to enable the impact to be reduced but more energy to be produced to excite the whole plate without damage or without introducing non-linear responses, a resilient material (rubber or plastic) is introduced between the hammer and plate.

In the current investigation the shaker was used to demonstrate the modes of vibration of the plates and the impact hammer was utilised to obtain the transfer functions and the first four frequency modes.

In order to investigate the mode shapes of vibration for these plates, it is necessary to measure two parameters at each resonant frequency of the plate (fig 3). These are:

- (a) the displacement amplitude at a sufficient number of points,
- (b) the corresponding phase relationship between these points.

This is demonstrated in the section discussing the experimental procedure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Six composite plates (three quasi-isotropic and three orthotropic) of aspect ratio 1.25 were made. The three quasi-isotropic plates were manufactured from three chopped strand glass mats (each of weight 450 gm/m^2), in a polyester resin matrix; the final thickness was (2.4 ± 0.1) mm. The three orthotropic plates were fabricated from bidirectional glass fibre fabric: plain weave 428 (330 gm/m^2) in a polyester resin matrix; the final thickness of this composite was (2.0 ± 0.1) mm.

The strips of composite representing the stiffeners were manufactured from randomly orientated glass fibre in a polyester resin matrix; the strip had a total thickness of 6 mm and a depth of 6.8 mm. The strips were bonded onto the plates with epoxy resin. Likewise strips of bidirectional glass reinforcement were manufactured having thickness and depth of 6mm and 7mm respectively.

In order to obtain a near free/free boundary condition the plates were suspended vertically from a frame by elastics attached to the mid-points of its four corners. The suspension gives rigid body modes of vibration of the plate at very low frequencies (in the range of 3-5 Hz) compared with the lowest plate material frequency. The fully fixed boundary condition was achieved by clamping the plates between two steel frames with four bolts per side as shown in fig 4; the whole system was then fixed into a strong and stiff timber frame. The fixed/free plate boundary conditions were fully clamped along the two longitudinal edges and were free on the other two edges; the system was then fixed in the frame described above.

Vibration pick-up for several points on the plate nodes was made and at each point the motion of the accelerometer was recorded. Another pick-up was placed at a fixed point which was used as a phase reference to determine whether the plate motion at various points is in or out of phase.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The natural frequencies of grp rectangular plates can be modified by incorporating stiffeners. The mode shapes of unstiffened plates will indicate the areas of high amplitude where stiffeners could be positioned to reduce the amplitude but they must be positioned away from nodal lines. The relationship between the stiffener and the plate geometrical dimensions and the stiffener mass value must be such as to minimize the maximum deflection. The effect of the stiffener is significant in

increasing the frequency for fully clamped and clamped/free plates where only bending modes of vibration are present. However, for the completely free plates where both bending and torsional modes of vibration are present, the effect that stiffeners have on the torsional modes is minimal.

The maximum deflection in unstiffened plates can be reduced to zero at that position by the introduction of stiff stiffeners and the maximum amplitude of vibration will be distributed on either side of the stiffener. The plate will then have the appearance of being divided into two plates with dimensions of $(a \times b/2)$ and a clamped edge along the length of the stiffener.

The mode shapes of the unstiffened plates do not depend upon the plate mechanical properties and its thickness but do depend upon the lateral dimensions of the plate and upon its boundary conditions. However, for stiffened plates the mode shape is dependent upon the mechanical and geometric properties of the stiffener and upon the equivalent properties for the plate. This has been demonstrated in figs 5, 6 and 7, where it will be seen that, for fully clamped conditions and a thickness of composite 2.4mm the frequency of the first mode of vibration of the plate with one stiffener has a value of 148 Hz and this is greater than the frequency of the first mode of the plate with three stiffeners which has a value of only 142 Hz. For the plate of 2.0 mm thickness the corresponding frequencies are 169.77 Hz and 193.12 Hz respectively.

If three stiffeners are employed to stiffen a rectangular plate it does not necessarily imply that the fundamental frequency of this plate will be greater than that for the single stiffener plate; the boundary conditions must also be considered. It can be seen in fig 6 that for the case of a free/clamped rectangular composite plate of thickness 2.4mm, in mode 1 there is an increase in frequency, but for a fully clamped condition with three stiffeners there is a lower fundamental frequency than for the single stiffened plate. Also it can be seen that for the case of the rectangular plate with free/free boundary conditions, the frequencies for the three stiffeners and for both thicknesses of plate are less than those for the single stiffener case.

Plates with high stiffness-to-weight ratio will have higher fundamental frequencies than those with lower ratios; this has been demonstrated with the 2.0mm bidirectional and 2.4 mm randomly orientated fibre composites.

The solutions to the fundamental and the first three harmonics, and the percentage difference between analytical and experimental results are given in table 1 for fully clamped boundary conditions. For the first three modes of vibration the mathematical solutions are lower than those obtained from the analytical ones; in addition, the experimental solutions are lower than those from the mathematical ones. The shaker in the experimental technique adds an additional mass to the plate system which has not been considered in the theoretical or analytical solutions, consequently this source of inaccuracy will reduce slightly the frequency value of the experimental result. Fully fixed conditions are difficult to realise in vibration and impact work and the difference between the analytical and experimental results are no doubt from this cause.

The finite element and Gorman's [3] frequency predictions for the isotropic flat plates were compared and it was noted that there is a non-monotonic frequency sequence between both techniques; for some modes the natural frequencies are higher whereas for others the frequencies are lower. The source of these variations is believed to be related to the equivalent mass values and some of the corresponding mode shapes. Downs [4] has undertaken work on this problem.

OBSERVATIONS

The analytical and experimental analyses of the plates given in this paper reinforces the fact that vibration behaviour of complicated systems must not be dependent upon one analysis procedure only. Comprehensive modelling of a finite element solution from an experimental procedure should be undertaken before parameter studies are made.

For rectangular grp composite plates, an effective method of removing the natural frequencies of the system from the region where excitation energy is being produced is to optimise the dynamic properties. This may be achieved by minimizing the maximum deflection by the addition of transverse stiffeners of suitable stiffness-to-weight ratio.

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TABLE 1 THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISON
OF NATURAL FREQUENCIES OF VARIOUS FULLY CLAMPED COMPOSITE
RECTANGULAR PLATES

	Mode Number	Methods				Errors %		
		(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(a) & (b)	(b) & (c)	(b) & (d)
		Exact	F.E.M.	Exp. 1	Exp. 2			
Zero Stiffener	1	84.16	84.22	81.00	85.00	-0.07	3.82	-0.93
	2	147.89	148.60	146.00	151.00	-0.48	1.75	-1.61
	3	192.94	197.04	187.00	178.00	-2.13	5.09	9.66
	4	251.29	246.45	249.00	236.00	1.93	2.21	4.24
One Stiffener	1	-	148.00	144.00	137.00	-	2.70	7.43
	2	-	155.57	151.00	139.00	-	2.94	10.65
	3	-	257.75	249.00	260.00	-	3.39	-0.87
	4	-	268.82	262.00	270.00	-	2.54	-0.44
Three stiffeners	1	-	142.08	140.00	131.00	-	1.46	7.80
	2	-	185.04	177.00	180.00	-	4.34	2.72
	3	-	279.90	273.00	269.00	-	3.54	3.89
	4	-	361.75	356.00	363.00	-	1.59	-0.35

- (a) Exact: Gorman's frequencies prediction
 (b) F.E.M.: Finite Element Method using ABAQUS
 (c) Exp. 1: Derived from system Analysis (Shaker and Oscilloscope)
 (d) Exp. 2: Derived from signal Analysis (Hammer and F.F.T.)

Figure 1. Plates with different number of stiffeners

Figure 2. Division of a stiffened plate into a large number of finite elements.

Figure 3. Demonstration of mode shapes by the method of accelerometers.

Figure 4. Exploded view of plate-clamping apparatus.

(a)

(b)

Dashed lines: Original mesh

Solid lines: Displaced mesh.

Figure 5.

First four theoretical mode shapes of completely free rectangular composite plates with different numbers of transverse stiffeners.

(a) Lay-up 3 plies (GR)_s = 2.4mm plate thickness

(b) Lay-up: 6 plies (0⁰, 90⁰)_s = 2.0mm plate thickness

(a)

Dashed lines: Original mesh
Solid lines: Displaced mesh

(b)

Figure 6.
First four theoretical mode shapes of free/clamped rectangular composite plates with different numbers of transverse stiffeners.

- (a) Lay-up: 3 plies $(R, \bar{R})_s =$
plate thickness 2.4mm
- (b) Lay-up: 6 plies $(J^0, 9J^0)_s =$
plate thickness 2.0mm

Dashed lines: Original mesh

Solid lines: Displaced mesh

Figure 7.

First four theoretical mode shapes of fully clamped rectangular composite plates with different numbers of stiffeners.

(a) Lay-up: 3 plies
(R,R)_s = 2.4mm
plate thickness

(b) Lay-up: 6 plies
(0⁰, 9J⁰)_s = 2.0mm
plate thickness